

Graph Neural Networks for Hybrid Beamforming in MIMO Rate Splitting Multiple Access

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Abstract—In this paper, we investigate the use of self-supervised data-driven schemes for digital precoder optimization of hybrid analog-digital beamforming in the downlink of a Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) Rate Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) system. We propose two architectures based on Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) respectively, and analyze their achievable sum-rate performance in the overloaded regime as the system scales up. We use conventional schemes such as Zero Forcing (ZF) and Weighted Minimum Mean Square Error (WMMSE) precoding as benchmarks. Additionally, we compare their complexity in terms of the number of trainable parameters and number of operations, where GNN models have been found out to be scalable solutions.

Index Terms—Graph Neural Network, Deep Learning, Hybrid Beamforming, RSMA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Rate Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) has been pointed out as a unifying framework of existing MA schemes - orthogonal multiple access (OMA), space division multiple access (SDMA) and non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) [1]. RSMA has been shown to outperform NOMA [1] [2] in multi-input multi-output (MIMO) settings, both in terms of sum multiplexing gain and efficient use of Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC). RSMA enhances the benefits of MU-MIMO by achieving higher data rates and spectral efficiency, especially when users are closer together and under imperfect Channel State Information at Transmitter (CSIT). All these observations have led to the recommendation of 3GPP RAN to consider a study item on RSMA in Rel-19 [3].

The simplest and most practical RSMA scheme is 1-layer Rate Splitting (RS), which is the basic building block of almost all existing RSMA schemes. It involves transmission of common message symbols (common to all users) followed by SIC and decoding of individual private messages. The precoder optimization plays a key role in interference management of the common and private streams in the system. In massive MIMO systems, the use of fully-digital beamforming (FDB) where each antenna is equipped with a dedicated radio frequency (RF) chain leads to significant power consumption and hardware expenses. The adoption of hybrid analog-digital

beamforming architectures based on phase shifters achieves the same beamforming gain at a much reduced complexity and power consumption. The widely adopted Weighted Minimum Mean Square Error (WMMSE) algorithm has been applied in [2] [4] to obtain precoders in the RSMA system, but only for the FDB case. On the contrary, [5] introduces Sampled Average Approximation (SAA)-WMMSE method under known CSIT and CSIT error distribution. The application of the above variations of WMMSE is computationally intensive as the number of transmit antennas and users in the system increases. Alternatively, sub-optimal schemes involve the use of zero-forcing (ZF) for obtaining the private precoders and eigenvector corresponding to largest eigenvalue (using singular value decomposition (SVD)) for the common precoder [6] [7]. However, the system capacity achieved is not satisfactory, especially in large RSMA settings.

As for the application of Deep Learning (DL) to enhance the WMMSE algorithm, a number of works can be found in the literature [8]–[10]. In an RSMA setting, the authors in [10] intentionally over-fit a multilayer perceptron (MLP) to learn the precoders of the WMMSE algorithm for the realization of one channel and use it as a starting reference for subsequent ones, which are inspired by meta-learning-based precoder design. The need for labeled datasets [11] is eliminated by training the system in a self-supervised manner [8] [12], that is, by resorting to a customized loss function dependent on the *channel response* instead of using precoder instances. Among self-supervised approaches, [12] uses transformers to perform precoder optimization in an end-to-end RSMA setting with analog and digital beamforming networks.

This paper investigates the use of Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) for RSMA hybrid beamforming. Since precoders are permutation equivariant with respect to the channel matrix, GNN architectures offer more scalable solutions for the MIMO beamforming optimization task [8]. The phase shifters of analog beamformers are usually fixed because the second order statistics of the channel remain constant over long periods of time. Hence, we focus on the application of GNN and MLP for digital precoding in HBF. Similar to [12], we train the neural networks in a self-supervised manner for each new channel realization to output the digital precoders. We evaluate the performance-complexity trade-off involved in usage of lighter models which are not as computationally intensive as the transformers (that have

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Fig. 1. One-layer RS model with K users. The common stream s_c is intended for all users, whereas private streams s_k are individual to each user.

multiple self-attention and MLP sub-layers) used in [12].

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a downlink scenario of a multi-user RSMA system, where the Base Station (BS) is equipped with M transmit antennas and K_R radio-frequency chains serve K single-antenna users. The evaluation is conducted for 1-layer RS, where the message W_k intended for the k -th user is split at the transmitter into two sub-messages, namely, sub-message $W_{c,k}$ and private sub-message $W_{p,k}$. The sub-messages $W_{c,1}, \dots, W_{c,K}$ of all the users are combined into one message W_c and encoded into a common stream s_c using a codebook shared by all users. Although the entire common message W_c has to be decoded by all users, only the corresponding sub-message $W_{c,k}$ is of interest to the k -th user. The private sub-messages of all users $W_{p,1}, \dots, W_{p,K}$ are independently encoded into private streams s_1, \dots, s_K , which are decoded by the respective users (illustrated in Fig. 1). Therefore, $K + 1$ streams, i.e., $\mathbf{s} = [s_c, s_1, \dots, s_K]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{(K+1) \times 1}$ are created from the K messages W_1, \dots, W_K . The received signal at user k is given by

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{F}_{\text{RF}} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{F}_{\text{BB}} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}_k \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{\text{RF}} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times K_R}$ is the RF analog beamformer which should satisfy constant modulus constraint $|\mathbf{F}_{\text{RF}}| = 1/\sqrt{N_t}$, and $\mathbf{F}_{\text{BB}} \in \mathbb{C}^{K_R \times (K+1)}$ is the baseband digital beamformer. The digital beamforming vector for the common stream is represented as $\mathbf{f}_{\text{BB}(c)} \in \mathbb{C}^{K_R \times 1}$, while for the private stream is $\mathbf{f}_{\text{BB}(k)} \in \mathbb{C}^{K_R \times 1}$. The matrix \mathbf{A} is a diagonal matrix containing the values $\alpha_c, \alpha_k \in [0, 1]$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$, which are the power allocation coefficients of common and private message streams. They are assumed to be normalized, such that $\alpha_c^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^2 = 1$. The vector $\mathbf{h}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times M}$ is the channel of the k -th user modeled as Gaussian random variables with the entries being circularly symmetric and drawn independently for each realization; \mathbf{n}_k denotes i.i.d. Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance $\sigma_{n,k}^2$.

At the receiver, each user first decodes the common stream s_c into W_c by treating the interference from all private streams

as noise. Using Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC), W_c is then re-encoded, precoded, and subtracted from the received signal such that user- k decodes its private stream s_k into $W_{p,k}$ by treating the remaining interference from the other private streams as noise. Finally, the k -th user reconstructs the original message by extracting $W_{c,k}$ from W_c , and combining $W_{c,k}$ with $W_{p,k}$ into W_k . The signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) at user k for decoding the common and private streams are given by the respective equations below.

$$\gamma_{c,k} = \frac{|\alpha_c \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{F}_{\text{RF}} \mathbf{f}_{\text{BB}(c)}|^2}{\sum_{q=1}^K |\alpha_q \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{f}_{\text{BB}(q)}|^2 + \sigma_{n,k}^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma_{p,k} = \frac{|\alpha_k \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{F}_{\text{RF}} \mathbf{f}_{\text{BB}(k)}|^2}{\sum_{q=1, q \neq k}^K |\alpha_q \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{F}_{\text{RF}} \mathbf{f}_{\text{BB}(q)}|^2 + \sigma_{n,k}^2} \quad (3)$$

The achievable rate of the common stream of user k is $R_{c,k} = \log_2(1 + \gamma_{c,k})$, while that of the private stream is $R_{p,k} = \log_2(1 + \gamma_{p,k})$. As the common stream must be decoded by all the users in the system, it must be transmitted at a rate not exceeding a global common minimum, namely, $R_c = \min\{R_{c,1}, \dots, R_{c,K}\}$. Thus, the achievable sum-rate R_{sum} for a given analog and digital precoding matrix $\mathcal{F} = \{\mathbf{F}_{\text{RF}}, \mathbf{F}_{\text{BB}}\}$ reads

$$R_{\text{sum}}(\mathcal{F}) = R_c + \sum_{k=1}^K R_k \quad (4)$$

A. Conventional Precoder Solutions

For the analog precoders \mathbf{F}_{RF} , we use SVD on the overall channel matrix, which contains channels of all the users in the RSMA system. The phase of the eigenvectors associated with largest singular values are selected to build the RF precoders. To compute the digital precoders of the RSMA system, [2] [5] adopt the classical Weighted Minimum Mean Square Error (WMMSE) algorithm using the Sampled Average Approximation (SAA) method. Being an iterative and monotonically converging solution, the WMMSE is one of the theoretical benchmarks that reaches close-to-optimal performance in terms of achievable sum rate. However, SAA-WMMSE becomes computationally intensive and converges slower when the system scales up (higher number of transmit antennas and/or users). The problem is convex Quadratically Constrained Quadratic Program (QCQP) which can be solved using interior-point methods [5]. The optimization of (4) requires convex-optimizer subroutines which demands a very high number of operations as the system scales up [2], [12].

There exist sub-optimal solutions with lower complexity, as shown in [6], [7]. The common digital precoder $\mathbf{f}_{\text{BB}(c)}$ is designed as the principal eigenvector (i.e., eigenvector associated to the largest eigenvalue) of the overall channel matrix. This guarantees that the transmit power is maximized towards all the directions where users are present, without per-user priorities. The precoder vectors associated to the private streams are built to be completely orthogonal to each other using zero-forcing.

III. NEURAL NETWORKS FOR PRECODING

In this section, we formulate the problem of precoder optimization to be solved using neural networks (NN). Specifically, we look into the use of Graph Neural Network (GNN) and shallow (one layer) Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) architectures.

A. Problem Formulation

The precoders are optimized to maximize the sum-rate R_{sum} as defined below subject to a set of constraints:

$$\underset{\mathcal{F}(\cdot)}{\text{maximize}} \quad R_{\text{sum}}(\mathcal{F}) = R_c + \sum_{k=1}^K R_k \quad (5a)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad R_c \leq R_{c,k}, \forall k \in K \quad (5b)$$

$$|\mathbf{F}_{\text{RF}}| = 1/\sqrt{N_t} \quad (5c)$$

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{F}_{\text{BB}}\mathbf{F}_{\text{BB}}^H) \leq P_t \quad (5d)$$

where (5b) ensures common stream can be decoded by all the users; and (5c) is the constant modulus constraint on individual weights of analog beamformer, while (5d) is the transmit power constraint, P_t being the total transmit power.

As mentioned previously, the analog beamformer is computed using SVD in all the precoding schemes. The neural network-based precoders considered in this work take as input the *effective* channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{F}_{\text{RF}} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times K_R}$ and output the precoding matrix $\widehat{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{BB}}$. Thus, we have

$$\widehat{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{BB}} = f(\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}; \boldsymbol{\theta})$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ denotes the trainable parameters of the NN. The training of the NN is performed in a self-supervised manner by minimizing the negative sum rate, that is

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}^* = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} -R_{\text{sum}}(f(\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}; \boldsymbol{\theta})). \quad (6)$$

As the SINR of the common and private streams depend on the precoders, the neural networks are trained to achieve precoder optimization using gradient descent and backpropagation.

B. Graph Neural Network

The RSMA precoding problem can be viewed as a mapping from $K \times K_R$ *effective* channel matrix to $K_R \times (K + 1)$ precoding matrix. The K_R RF chains and K users are depicted as nodes of a graph, while the edges of the graph represent the MIMO channel, with $N_E = K_R \cdot K$ being the total number of edges of the graph (see Fig. 2). The L -layer GNN consists of: (i) one input layer depicting the wireless network as a graph with each edge containing the real and imaginary values of corresponding channel coefficient; (ii) one output layer with each of the edges holding the estimated private precoder coefficients, while the transmit nodes contain the common precoder coefficients; and (iii) $L - 2$ hidden layers that implement the Message Passing Algorithm (MPA) with $d_l (l = 2, \dots, L - 2)$ edge features each.

Message Passing Algorithm (MPA) The embedding of each edge (t, r) in layer l is represented as $\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^l$. At the input layer $l = 1$, it holds the real and imaginary coefficients of the channel along the particular edge i.e., $\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^1 =$

$[\text{Re}(h_{t,r}), \text{Im}(h_{t,r})]^T$. In each of the hidden layers, the operations consist of message-passing iterations and an update step, which is expressed as below

$$\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)} = \text{UPDATE}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}$ and $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}$ are the messages aggregated from the neighboring nodes of edge (t, r) , which is defined as

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)} = \text{AGGREGATE}^{(l)} \left(\{ \mathbf{z}_{(t,x)}^{(l)}, \forall x \in \mathcal{N}(t) \} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)} = \text{AGGREGATE}^{(l)} \left(\{ \mathbf{z}_{(x,r)}^{(l)}, \forall x \in \mathcal{N}(r) \} \right) \quad (9)$$

The mechanism of MPA in the l -th hidden layer is as shown in Fig. 2. It should be noted that the UPDATE and AGGREGATE are differentiable functions [13] that need to be defined.

Fig. 2. GNN for RSMA precoder computation, visualized for a single edge $(0,0)$ in the graph. The message passing operations are shown in (a) message aggregation at RF chain nodes $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}$ and (b) message aggregation at user nodes $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}$, while (c) shows the updated edge feature as per update rule (7).

The update rule for the edges, which accounts for the private precoder coefficients, in (7) can be expanded as below

$$\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)} = \text{UPDATE}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$= \sigma \left(\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}^{(l)} \mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)} + \mathbf{W}_t^{(l)} \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} + \mathbf{W}_r^{(l)} \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)}$ denotes the hidden representation of the edge (t, r) at the $(l + 1)$ layer of the GNN, $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a non-linear activation function. The update rule of transmit nodes which represents the common precoder coefficients is as follows.

$$\mathbf{z}_{(t)}^{(l+1)} = \text{UPDATE}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{z}_{(t)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$= \sigma \left(\mathbf{W}_{\text{node}}^{(l)} \mathbf{z}_{(t)}^{(l)} + \mathbf{W}_n^{(l)} \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (13)$$

The matrices $\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_{\text{node}}^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_t^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_r^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_n^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{l+1} \times d_l}$ are the learnable weights of GNN to be optimized using stochastic gradient descent. The dimensions d_{l+1} and d_l of the weight matrices determine the number of features in layers $(l + 1)$ and l , respectively. For the RSMA precoding problem, the input layer of GNN has $d_0 = 2$ features (real and imaginary parts of the channel coefficient). In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions

in all hidden layers. At the output layer, a linear activation function is used to compute the precoders.

Similar to [14] [15], we define the message *aggregation* (via the AGGREGATE function in (8) and (9)) passed between the nodes as follows

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}(t)|} \sum_{r' \in \mathcal{N}(t)} \mathbf{z}_{(t,r')}^{(l)} \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}(r)|} \sum_{t' \in \mathcal{N}(r)} \mathbf{z}_{(t',r)}^{(l)} \quad (15)$$

At the output layer, a readout function is used which sums the learned edge and node features. This is followed by a linear layer that outputs the real and imaginary parts of the precoding matrix $\widehat{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{BB}}$. To fulfill the power constraint, a power normalization layer is applied to the output, which consists of a scalar normalization given by

$$\widehat{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{BB}}^{\text{norm}} = \zeta \widehat{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{BB}} \quad (16)$$

with $\zeta = \sqrt{P_T / \text{Tr}(\widehat{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{BB}} \widehat{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{BB}}^H)}$.

C. Multi-Layer Perceptron

The self-supervised precoder design problem can also be solved using MLPs. Specifically, it can be cast into a regression task where:

- The input of the DNN is the overall *effective* channel matrix \mathbf{H}_{eff} reshaped into a row vector $\mathbf{t} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}) \otimes [0, 1]]$.
- The output is the computed precoders $\mathbf{p} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\widehat{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{BB}}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\widehat{\mathbf{F}}_{\text{BB}}) \otimes [0, 1]]$

The L -layer MLP consists of: (i) one input layer with $2KK_R$ elements (the real and imaginary parts of the channel matrix); (ii) one output layer with $2K_R(K+1)$ neurons; and (iii) $L-2$ hidden layers with N_l neurons each, $l = 2, \dots, L-1$. This MLP defines a mapping $f(\mathbf{t}, \Phi) : \mathbb{R}^{2KK_R} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{2K_R(K+1)}$ of an input vector \mathbf{t} onto an output vector \mathbf{r}_L through L iterative processing steps:

$$\mathbf{r}_l = f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l); \quad l = 1 \dots L \quad (17)$$

where $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}, \phi_l) : \mathbb{R}^{N_{l-1}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the mapping associated to the l -th layer. Such mapping depends on the output from the previous layer and also the parameter set of the concerned layer, ϕ_l , with $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L]$ denoting the set of all parameters in the model.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we first assess the performance of the proposed *GNN* and *MLP* schemes in terms of the Achievable Sum-Rate (ASR), alongside the impact of CSIT error. This is followed by the computational complexity of the precoding schemes. The scenarios considered are: $K = \{2, 8, 32\}$ *single*-antenna users, and $M = \{3, 9, 32\}$ transmit antennas, respectively. The number of RF chains in each case is set to be $K_R = K$. As for the power allocation coefficients $\{\alpha_c, \alpha_k\}$ of ZF and WMMSE benchmarks, 90% of P_t is allocated to the common precoder, 10% is equally distributed

among the K private precoders (similar to [5], [10]). This ensures low error propagation from common stream detection to private stream detection due to improper SIC. In the case of neural networks, they are estimated as part of the precoder output. The neural networks are trained for each new channel realization to compute the precoders at an SNR of 20dB. This set of precoders is used to compute the sum rate across an SNR range of -10 dB to 30 dB. For the Adam optimizer, the learning rate is set to 0.01. All the neural networks are trained for 100 epochs, to ensure they reach convergence.

Across all system settings, the number of hidden layers $L = 3$, number of neurons in the MLPs $N_l = 32$, while the number of edge features of GNNs $d_l = 2$. We show that the simple architecture of these neural networks are able to generalize well for varying RSMA scenarios without the need for grid-search hyperparameter optimization.

A. Achievable Sum-Rate

The neural networks take as input the *effective* channel matrix \mathbf{H}_{eff} to compute the precoders. As benchmarks, we have followed the implementation of WMMSE for RSMA [2], and the sub-optimal solution based on zero-forcing (ZF).

Fig. 3 depicts the achievable sum-rate as a function of the SNR for all the scenarios considered, averaged over 100 channel realizations. For the case of $K = 2$ users, the gap between ZF and WMMSE performance is marginal, with the neural networks exhibiting similar performance to ZF. In the case of $K = 8$ users, neural network-based precoders offer substantial gain in the mid-SNR region. The initialization of WMMSE with ZF precoders ensures improved performance, but is not guaranteed to reach global optimality. It can be outperformed, as is the case for both the MLP and GNN precoders in the mid-SNR region. On the contrary, in the overloaded scenario of 32 users, ZF does not offer satisfactory performance, whereas the neural network-based schemes are virtually identical to that of the WMMSE algorithm across most of the SNR range, with marginal difference at high SNR. When compared to ZF, the neural network based schemes offer almost three orders of improvement at 20dB.

B. Impact of Channel Estimation

The quality of the channel state information at the transmitter (CSIT) may have a substantial impact on the achievable sum rate of the precoding policies. The noisy channel estimate $\widehat{\mathbf{H}}$ (instead of \mathbf{H}) is modeled as $\widehat{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{H} + \mathbf{N}$, where $\mathbf{N} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times M}$ represents zero-mean AWGN of variance β^2 . With imperfect precoders, the orthogonality of the private messages is not preserved, leading to poor ASR. In Fig. 4 (x-axis in log scale), one observes that the ASR decreases as the noise variance increases. The degradation rate has been analyzed at different SNR, solid lines depict 30 dB, while the dashed lines represent 20 dB. For the system with 8 users (highly loaded scenario, top), the ZF benchmark degrades at a similar rate to MLP and GNN schemes for $\beta^2 > 10^{-2}$. At 20dB, ZF offers lower system capacity than that of MLP and GNN. For 32 users (overloaded scenario, bottom), the

Fig. 3. Achievable Sum-Rate of the precoder optimization schemes.

performance gap between the ZF benchmark and NN schemes is substantially large.

C. Computational Complexity Analysis

1) *Number of trainable parameters*: The total number of trainable parameters depends on (i) the number of hidden layers in MLPs, which is 1 (shallow architecture to keep computational complexity low); (ii) the number of hidden features (d_l) for GNNs (iii) the number of inputs $2KK_R$; (iv) the number of neurons at the output layer, which is the total number of real values to be estimated (real and imaginary

Fig. 4. Achievable Sum Rate for various precoding policies vs. noise variance β^2 of CSIT, for scenario with 8 users (top) and 32 users (bottom). The solid lines correspond to SNR 30dB, while the dashed are for 20dB.

precoder matrix coefficients) $N_L = 2K_R(K + 1)$; (v) the number of neurons at the hidden layers (N_l) for DNNs.

As depicted in Fig. 5, GNNs record the least number of trainable parameters compared to MLPs for the whole range of number of transmit antennas and users. This stark difference (note y-axis is in log-scale) is because in GNNs, the same weights ($\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}, \mathbf{W}_{\text{node}}, \mathbf{W}_t, \mathbf{W}_r, \mathbf{W}_n$) are used for each edge and node respectively to compute the precoder coefficients, unlike MLP which demands higher number of neurons as the system scales up, which validates that GNNs are scalable architectures [13].

2) *Number of operations*: Since the neural networks are trained in a self-supervised manner, the number of operations needed include the operations performed in both the forward pass and backward propagation of gradients. This is repeated over a number of epochs (E) for both MLP and GNN. The computational complexity in both the forward and backward propagation are related and dependent on the number of weights in neural network. An overview of the complexity analysis is shown in Table I, where M denotes the number of transmit antennas and K the number of users. Zero-forcer being the simplest solution involves a few matrix multiplications and matrix inverse computation. It should be noted that each

TABLE I
COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY OF DIFFERENT PRECODER SCHEMES.

Variable	ZF	MLP	GNN	WMMSE
Multiplications	$\mathcal{O}(K^3 + K^2M)$	$\mathcal{O}(E(MKN_I + N_I^2L))$	$\mathcal{O}(E(MKd_1^2L))$	$\mathcal{O}(ED(M^3 + K^2M^2))$
Additions	$\mathcal{O}(K^3 + K^2M)$	$\mathcal{O}(EN_I L)$	$\mathcal{O}(E(MKd_1^2L + M^2Kd_1L + MK^2d_1L))$	$\mathcal{O}(ED(M^3 + K^2M^2))$

Fig. 5. Number of trainable parameters for different neural networks.

complex multiplication requires 4 real multiplication and 2 real additions, while a complex addition requires 2 real additions.

The number of operations for MLP depends on the number of layers L , the number of neurons N_I , and the respective input and output layer size. As for GNN, the number of edges scale up as the number of transmit antennas and users increase; the message passing algorithm accounts for a significant number of operations. As for the WMMSE solution, apart from matrix multiplications involved for computing the equalizers and user weights [5], the complexity of the convex optimization subroutine (CVX) increases dramatically at the rate of $\mathcal{O}(M^3)$. The CVX subroutine is an iterative solver that is called D times for each epoch of the WMMSE algorithm. Being an alternating optimization algorithm, it accounts for the highest number of operations compared to any other scheme [16]. This accounts for ED number of iterations for WMMSE, while the GNN and MLP is only dependent on E .

Thus, neural network based solutions achieve similar performance as WMMSE, at a fraction of the computational complexity, especially in large RSMA settings. As the total number of trainable weights also reflect on the computational complexity [17], it can be deduced from Fig. 5 that the scalable GNN solution accounts for lower number of operations than MLP.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The use of machine learning based precoder policies shows benefits in terms of computation complexity when compared with traditional iterative based benchmarks. For MIMO-RSMA setting, MLPs and GNNs trained in a self-supervised manner achieve similar performance to that of WMMSE

solution and outperform sub-optimal ZF by several orders of magnitude in selected scenarios. GNNs prove to be a scalable solution requiring fewer trainable parameters. The study will be extended to evaluate precoders for non-linear channels.

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